

A CNN Algorithm to detect Alzheimer's Disease with EEG and MoCA score

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Alzheimer's Disease is a neurodegenerative disorder and the most common type of dementia. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), by 2025 an estimated 1.2 billion persons aged 60 and over will be living with dementia, with approximately three-quarters of them residing in developing countries. Since this disease is not solely age-related and there is no definitive cure for it, early diagnosis can be very helpful. Although memory impairment is the most obvious symptom of Alzheimer's disease (AD), sometimes it is not diagnosed easily. Electroencephalogram signal (EEG) is a non-invasive way to investigate AD in the early stage. Moreover, the MoCA cognitive assessment test (MoCA) can assess the cognitive abilities such as memory. In this research, a multi-faceted approach has been proposed to automating this method. The proposed approach includes four stages: feature extraction, merging and final classification. As a feature extractor, a shallow Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) collected features from EEG eyes-closed (EC) and MoCA scores. In the merging phase, SVM and logistic regression were used to merge extracted features from CNN. Finally, by evaluating various machine learning models, SVM and logistic regression models were utilized as classifiers. The experimental results indicate 97.83% or 99.97% accuracy, 97.99% precision, 97.82% recall, and 97.84% F1-score for AD detection.

Background and Aim: Among the Machine Learning algorithms used to detect Alzheimer's disease (AD) using an electroencephalogram (EEG) processing, mention can be made of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Autoencoder (AE), Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), Deep Belief Network (DBN), Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM), Multilayer Perceptron Neural Network (MLPNN), and Optimized Deep Neural Network. (Lin et al., 2017) The Support Vector Machine algorithm (SVM) algorithm can deal with the challenges of classifying imbalanced samples more effectively. Another research indicates that SVM has more advantages than other approaches like error back-propagation models. Wan et al. showed that the correlation metrics extracted from EEG signals can effectively reflect neurophysiological changes and discriminate patients with cognitive impairment from healthy control group. (Wan et al., 2018). In a study conducted by Thomas Rotkofsky and colleagues, multi-scale entropy patterns in the working memory visual pattern were used to detect Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) in adults. The Random Forest algorithm also achieved high average accuracy of over 80% in automatically distinguishing between healthy individuals with normal cognitive function and individuals with MCI. (Rotkofsky et al., 2021) Moreover, in the same year, a study by Rosini and colleagues used the SVM on biomarkers for MCI people at risk of early-onset AD. The article demonstrated that By classifying data in an 80-20 ratio for model training and testing, an accuracy of approximately 97% was achieved. (Rosini et al., 2021) In addition Foladi and colleagues presented a database include EEG data from 19 channels involving 61 healthy individuals, 56 MCI patients, and 63 AD patients was used. Time-Frequency Representation (TFR) was used for feature extraction. Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT) with the Mexican Hat function (MHf) as the mother wavelet for TFR was selected. The average accuracy obtained for the modified convolutional network and the autoencoder convolutional network was 92% and 89%, respectively. The proposed networks not only achieved a 10% increase in classification accuracy but also outperformed similar networks in handling similar data classes.

Furthermore, the accuracy obtained from the proposed networks was significantly higher than conventional machine learning methods. In another article examined a total of 890 signals (189 MCI patients, 330 Alzheimer's patients, 125 individuals with other cognitive impairments, and 246 healthy individuals) using the Random Forest algorithm, EEG biomarkers identified achieved an accuracy of over 70% in classifying three levels: HC, MCI, and AD. (Bin Jiao, 2023)

Our purpose is to make a model using Convolutional Neural Network algorithm (CNN) to accurately detect Alzheimer's disorder with non-invasive test data such as EEG and MoCA tests.

Methods: In this study, two groups with AD (24 patients with AD in the moderate stage and 27 patients with AD in the early stage) and one group of healthy control (51 individuals) were selected. For each participant, at least 2 minutes of the *eyes-closed* (EC) EEG signals were recorded and the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) questionnaire was subsequently taken in one session. MoCA scores ranged from 26 to 30 for healthy individuals, 18 to 25 for the ones with early-stage AD, and 10 to 17 for patients with AD in the moderate stage. In the preprocessing stage, a Spiking Neural Network (SNN) method was utilized. Then, optimal features from Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) were extracted. These features were integrated into the SVM model framework, resulting in a model with an accuracy of 97.83% for distinguishing Alzheimer's from healthy individuals.

Results: The final model which includes the extracted features from CNN, combined with the SVM, achieves an accuracy of 97.83%, precision of 97.99%, recall of 97.82% and f1-score 97.84.

Conclusion: This research established a new model of CNN to discriminate AD. The main advantage is to integrate two features of cognitive assessment indicating brain functions and EEG signals arising from the excitable nature of neurons. We also upgrade the model evaluations by combination of CNN and SVM algorithms.

Keywords: Montreal Cognitive Assessment, Electroencephalogram (EEG), Convolutional neural network, Alzheimer's Disease.